

Intelligent Bus Scheduling System Using IoT: Improving Efficiency, Safety, and Passenger Experience

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Abstract

Current public transportation systems face significant challenges, including inefficiencies in scheduling, overcrowding, and safety concerns. This paper introduces a novel, IoT-based bus scheduling automation system designed to address these issues. By integrating GPS tracking, real-time Ticketing data captured by devices handled by bus conductors, and Machine Learning to analyze and predict crowd strength, our system dynamically adjusts bus schedules to match passenger demand. As new passengers board and tickets are issued, the ticketing device sends real-time logs to a Central Server. The server aggregates this data from all buses across the city, continuously updating records of passenger counts, boarding locations, and travel patterns. This collected data is then processed and analyzed using machine learning models, which identify trends, predict demand fluctuations, and generate insights for optimizing bus schedules. The system considers historical trends, external factors such as holidays and peak hours, and predefined operational constraints to recommend adjustments in bus allocation.

This approach not only optimizes resource allocation and reducing unnecessary fuel consumption but also enhances safety by minimizing overcrowding, which can help prevent petty crimes and harassment, ensuring a safe space. With the potential to improve passenger experience and trust in public transportation, this system offers a scalable solution, especially for urban mobility challenges. Future applications could include integration with smart city initiatives to promote

efficient transportation, route management and safety.

Keywords: IoT-based bus scheduling automation system, GPS Tracking, Ticketing Device, Resource Optimization

1. Introduction

Public transportation is a vital component of urban infrastructure, yet it often struggles with inefficiencies and unreliability. Traditional bus scheduling methods typically rely on fixed timetables that fail to account for fluctuations in passenger demand, leading to overcrowding during peak hours and underutilization during off-peak times. This mismatch between supply and demand not only diminishes the user experience but also increases operational costs for bus operators. The integration of Internet of Things (IoT) devices and machine learning (ML) technologies offers a promising solution to these challenges. By leveraging IoT to collect real-time data on passenger movements and employing ML algorithms to predict demand, it becomes possible to adjust bus service intervals to align with actual passenger needs. This approach has the potential to enhance the efficiency, reliability, and sustainability of public transportation systems, ultimately contributing to more livable and connected cities.

2. Literature Survey

Paper Citation: Tielle Alexandre, Fla´via Bernardini, Jose´ Viterbo and Carlos Eduardo Pantoja “Machine Learning Applied to Public Transportation by Bus: A Systematic Literature Review”, Transportation Research Record 2022

Our system improves upon the approaches proposed in the paper by offering city-wide data aggregation, advanced time-series forecasting with ARIMAX, and proactive bus scheduling based on demand trends. Unlike existing solutions that focus on individual routes or specific timeframes, we collect daily passenger data across all buses in the city, providing a comprehensive view of **transit** patterns. While the paper discusses passenger flow prediction and long-term travel time estimation, it lacks a clear framework for adjusting bus schedules based on projected demand.

Additionally, while current ML-based models mainly focus on travel time prediction and demand estimation, they do not translate these insights into optimized scheduling decisions. Our approach directly uses demand forecasts to improve resource allocation, reducing overcrowding and preventing underutilization of buses. Furthermore, while some proposed solutions suggest using AVL, APC, and AFC systems for passenger flow estimation, we take a more structured, city-wide approach and have the potential to integrate IoT-based real-time passenger counts for improved accuracy. Unlike the existing fragmented approaches, our system provides a holistic, data-driven method for scheduling buses efficiently, helping authorities make long-term, evidence-based decisions rather than relying on static schedules or reactive adjustments.

Paper Citation: N. Jeyakkannan, Dr.C. Karthik, Dr.Vivek Lukose “ IoT Based Smart Bus System using wireless sensor networks”

Our proposed approach addresses several key limitations present in existing methods for bus scheduling and management. One of the primary issues with current approaches is the reliance on historical data and static predictions to estimate travel and arrival times. While these methods can provide reasonable accuracy under stable conditions, they fail to adapt to real-time fluctuations in passenger demand and changing traffic scenarios. In contrast, our system dynamically adjusts bus schedules by leveraging real-time ticketing data, GPS tracking, and passenger demand fluctuations, ensuring that bus frequency consistently matches current demand. Another critical gap in existing methods is the lack of focus on passenger safety and overcrowding management. Most existing systems primarily predict travel times and passenger flows without

actively mitigating overcrowding issues, which can lead to safety concerns and discomfort for passengers. Our solution directly addresses this problem by dynamically modifying bus frequency to reduce overcrowding, thereby enhancing passenger safety and minimizing the risk of petty crimes and harassment. Additionally, existing approaches tend to overlook fuel efficiency and resource optimization, as they are often designed solely to predict travel times and flows rather than adjust operations dynamically. Our system tackles this challenge by optimizing fuel usage through demand-driven scheduling, significantly reducing unnecessary trips and minimizing environmental impact. Moreover, scalability and integration with smart city initiatives are often not adequately considered in existing methods, which limits their adaptability to evolving urban transportation needs. Our solution is designed with scalability in mind, enabling seamless integration with broader smart city frameworks and supporting future advancements in public transportation management.

The original concept of statistical time series analysis was proposed by Yule [11] in 1927, who used AR(2) and AR(4) models to solve a problem of sunspot time series. After that, Box et al. [2] were the first researchers who introduced the Autoregressive Moving Average (ARMA) model. They discussed in detail the 5 steps of iterative model building, which includes model identification, estimation, diagnostic checking and control. Wang's [7] and Wei's [8] books, they offered specific methods and techniques to achieve the time series analysis. There are currently many applications of the time series method to the public transportation system as well as the society management. For instance, Gu et al. [6] used the ARMA model to forecast passenger flow for a bus hub in Shanghai. He basically followed 5 steps of iterative model building and chose a particular ARMA $(2n, 2n - 1)$ model to eventually achieve nearly 80% prediction accuracy. Similarly, Cao and Chang [4] used the ARIMA model to forecast the trends of tourist flow in Shanghai. Unlike Gu et al., Cao and Chang's research completely applied time series method in [2] and followed solely the 5 steps of iterative model building. Their research also highlighted the valuable insight that short-term accuracy is usually higher than mid-term or long-term accuracy, because the model they used is sensitive to the stationarity of the time series.

3. Proposed Method

Figure 1 Block Diagram of the Architecture Flow

Data Collection:

In our system, passenger data is collected using an **Electronic Ticketing Machine (ETM)**, an IoT-enabled device used by bus conductors to issue tickets to passengers. Over time, ETM machines have evolved significantly, incorporating advanced functionalities that enhance efficiency and connectivity. Modern ETM machines consist of several key components, including a central processing unit (CPU) that executes operations, a memory module for local data storage, a thermal printer for generating physical tickets, an inbuilt communication module for **data transmission**, and an interactive interface for conductors to input trip details and issue tickets. Typically, an ETM device is equipped with RAM ranging from 512MB to 2GB and ROM (internal storage) between 4GB and 16GB, depending on the manufacturer and model specifications.

The operation begins when a conductor enters the required trip details into the ETM. The interactive interface allows the conductor to select the passenger's boarding point and destination. The CPU processes this input, verifies predefined fare parameters, and generates a ticket with all relevant details. The thermal printer then prints the ticket, which is handed to the passenger. At the same time, the **ETM logs crucial data** such as the date, time, start location, and destination in its local memory. This step is repeated for every passenger boarding the bus, ensuring a comprehensive digital record of all ticket transactions.

To ensure data accuracy and prevent loss, the ETM temporarily stores the recorded transactions in its internal memory. At predefined intervals, the stored data is automatically transmitted to a cloud server using the integrated communication module. The communication module, which may consist of GSM (2G, 3G, 4G LTE), GPRS, Wi-Fi, or LPWAN (Low Power Wide Area Network) technologies, establishes a secure connection with the internet. The ETM initiates a data transfer request by first retrieving the locally stored transaction data. Before transmission, the data is formatted into a structured form to ensure compatibility with the cloud database. The communication module then transmits the formatted data packets securely over the network.

To facilitate this process, the ETM is preconfigured with server details, including the destination IP address and authentication credentials. Once the transmission process is initiated, the data packets travel through the communication module, passing through encryption and compression algorithms for security and efficiency. The cloud server, upon receiving the data, validates its integrity and stores it in the designated data warehouse or database. The cloud server plays a crucial role in organizing and managing the received data. It categorizes and structures passenger records for efficient storage and retrieval. Given the high volume of incoming data from multiple ETM devices citywide, a data warehouse or database is implemented to ensure scalability and advanced analytics capabilities.

Forecasting Methodology ARIMA:

Figure 2: Experiment flowchart, briefly including data processing, time series preprocessing, time series modeling and prediction Referred from: [Yinna Ye]

[Yinna Ye 11] The theoretical basis of this project is the weak stationary time series analysis. Before we introduce weak stationary time series models. Our model addresses the issue of weak stationarity in time series data by applying **preprocessing** techniques before fitting the ARIMA model. A time series is weakly stationary if its mean, variance, and autocovariance remain constant over time. However, bus fare and demand data often exhibit trends and seasonal variations due to external factors such as fuel prices, holidays, and economic changes. Directly applying ARIMA to such non-stationary data can lead to unreliable forecasts.

To ensure weak stationarity, we implement the following steps: **Differencing**: We apply first-order differencing to remove linear trends and make the time series stationary.

Log Transformation: If the variance is not constant over time, we apply a log or power transformation to stabilize fluctuations and ensure homoscedasticity.

[Yinna Ye] ARIMA modeling for the weekday-only data. We need to firstly test whether the time series is stationary. For this, we use the Augmented Dickey-Fuller Unit Root (ADF) test.

Time series forecasting plays a crucial role in predicting bus fare trends and passenger demand over time. Given our dataset, which consists of bus ID, time, date, origin, destination, and fare, the **AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA)** model is an effective approach to analyzing historical patterns and making accurate forecasts. The primary objective is to model the fare fluctuations over time and predict future fares based on past trends, allowing for better fare adjustments and demand management.

ARIMA works by combining three components **AutoRegression (AR)**, **Differencing (I for Integration)**, and **Moving Average (MA)**. The autoregressive component considers the dependency of current fare values on past fares, while the moving average component smooths out fluctuations by analyzing past error terms. Differencing, on the other hand, is used to make the data stationary, ensuring that statistical properties remain constant over time. The choice of ARIMA's parameters (p, d, q) is determined using Autocorrelation Function (ACF) and Partial Autocorrelation Function (PACF) plots, which help identify the order of AR and MA components required for an optimal fit.

RealTime Bus Scheduling using Dynamic Programming:

[J.E. Beasley 12] In this paper we consider the crew scheduling problem, that is the problem of assigning K crews to tasks with fixed start and finish times such that each crew does not exceed a limit on the total time it can spend working. This problem is formulated as a problem of finding K time limit constrained vertex disjoint paths which visit all vertices on a network.

This paper presents a **dynamic programming**-based approach to solving the bus crew scheduling problem, optimizing crew allocation while considering work constraints, duty linking, and rest periods. The proposed algorithm effectively assigns conductors and drivers to bus routes, maximizing crew utilization and minimizing unassigned trips.

Given a set of crews $C = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n\}$, each with a predefined role $r(c)$ (conductor or driver), maximum working hours $w_{\max}(c)$, and rest constraints $r_{\min}(c)$. A set of trips $T = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_m\}$, where each trip t has a start time $s(t)$, end time $e(t)$, and requires both a driver and a conductor. A set of buses $B = \{b_1, b_2, \dots, b_k\}$, each assigned trips from T , ensuring crew availability and duty continuity. The objective is to maximize crew utilization and minimize unassigned trips while ensuring compliance with work-hour limits, rest requirements, and linked duty constraints.

state = (*current_trip*, *remaining_hours*, *assigned_crew*)
 $dp[state] = \min(dp.get(previous_state, INF) + cost)$

This defines the key state variables in dynamic programming
current_trip: Tracks the ongoing trip.
remaining_hours: Ensures the crew does not exceed working hour limits.
assigned_crew: Ensures both a conductor and driver are assigned.
 This structured state representation allows efficient optimization of scheduling decisions.

for crew in available_crews:
if(crew.can_take_trip(trip) and
crew.remaining_hours >= trip.duration):
 new_state = (*next_trip*,
 crew.remaining_hours - trip.duration, crew.id)
 $dp[new_state] = \min(dp.get(new_state, INF),$
 $dp[current_state] + cost)$

The transition function determines the next valid state based on:

- Availability of the crew.
- Compliance with working hour limits.
- Assignment of the most suitable crew to the trip while ensuring optimal cost.

if crew.working_hours > max_shift_hours:
crew.resting = True
rest_end_time = current_time + REST_PERIOD

Crews exceeding shift limits are marked as resting. They cannot be assigned until their rest period ends. Real-world labor constraints are respected in scheduling.

fully_allocated = $\text{sum}(1 \text{ for trip in trips if } \text{trip.driver and trip.conductor})$
utilization_rate = $(\text{len}(\text{assigned_crews}) / \text{total_crews}) * 100$

Calculates the number of fully assigned trips. Computes crew utilization to assess scheduling efficiency. These statistics are essential for evaluating the model's performance. The dynamic programming approach significantly improves crew allocation efficiency while reducing the number of unassigned trips compared to traditional heuristic methods which takes a significant amount of time to schedule the crew members with respect to the required buses. Also this algorithm yields a **time complexity** of $O(T \times H \times C^2)$.

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